

color of feeding materials. It is fast moving and can be seen as a small moving dot on seedlings.

We attempted mass rearing of *T. palmarum* on different diets of fungi grown on several artificial media. It multiplied vigorously on *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Alternaria padwickii*, and *Curvularia* sp. On 10 different media, the mites grew best on 4% oatmeal agar (OMA). Egg-to-egg life cycle took 10-12 d on *F. moniliforme* grown on 4% OMA. Mites produced about 247 eggs, of which 210 hatched. About 167 adults emerged from the hatched larvae. Females reproduced parthenogenetically. There was no male population in the culture. □

***T. palmarum* populations in seedlings and leaf sheaths in 1983 dry and wet season nurseries, Cuttack, India.**

Variety	Populations (adults, juveniles, and eggs) 10 seedlings ^a
Ratna	34 b
Karuna	30 ab
CR1009	28 ab
CR1014	18 ab
Jaya	25 ab
Vijaya	19 ab
Pusa 2-21	2 a
Kalinga-I	16 ab
Supriya	15 ab
Jagannath	19 ab

^aAv of 10 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

T. palmarum mite, Cuttack, India.

Parasitization of yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* eggs

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We surveyed the IRRI farm to determine the extent of parasitization of YSB egg masses. Egg masses were randomly collected at weekly intervals from Jul to Aug 1984 from rice fields, 15-20 d after transplanting, and brought to the laboratory for collection of emerging parasites.

Three species of hymenopterous parasitoids — *Tetrastichus schoenobii*, *Teleonomus rowani*, and *Trichogramma japonicum* — were reared from 455 egg masses (Table 1). *T. schoenobii* was the most abundant among the species, parasitizing 95% of the eggs. *T. schoenobii* may be

the most efficient because two to four (av of three) host eggs are needed to complete the larval period. *T. japonicum* was so small that one to four (av of two) parasites developed from one host egg. Thus, in calculating percent parasitism by *T. schoenobii*, the number of emerged parasites is multiplied by 3. For *T. japonicum*, the number of emerged parasites is divided by 2 (see footnote to Table 1). Female parasites were five times as abundant as males.

Multiparasitization occurs in YSB egg masses (Table 2). Eighty-eight percent of the egg masses were parasitized by one or a combination of parasite species. The highest parasitization (35%) was by a combination of *T. rowani* and *T. japonicum*. □

Table 2. Multiparasitization of YSB egg masses (n = 485) by 3 parasites, IRRI, Jul-Aug 1984.

Parasite combination	Parasitization of egg masses (%)
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. schoenobii</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	9.8
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	34.6
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. schoenobii</i>	17.7
<i>T. schoenobii</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	11.5
<i>T. schoenobii</i>	9.5
<i>T. rowani</i>	3.2
<i>T. japonicum</i>	1.2
Total	87.5

Table 1. Percent parasitization of YSB egg masses and the sex ratio of the parasitoids, IRRI, Jul-Aug 1984.

Parasite	Egg masses (no.)	Eggs parasitized ^a (%)	Parasites (no./egg mass)		Stem borer larvae (no./egg mass)		Sex ratio (male:female)
			Emerged	Unemerged	Hatched	Unhatched	
<i>T. schoenobii</i>	46	94.7	18.7	2.0	1.5	2.0	5:1:1
<i>T. rowani</i>	15	45.3	20.8	10.3	18.4	19.1	5:3:1
<i>T. japonicum</i>	6	8.1	10.0	3.0	63.8	9.9	4:7:1

^aCalculated as: $T. schoenobii = \frac{(C \times 3) + (D \times 3)}{(A + D) + (C \times 3) + (D \times 3)} \times 100$

$T. rowani = \frac{C+D}{A+B+C+D} \times 100$

$T. japonicum = \frac{C/2 + D}{A + B + (C/2) + D} \times 100$

Where A = no. of hatched stem borer larvae, B = no. of unhatched stem borer larvae, C = no. of emerged parasites, and D = no. of unemerged parasites.

A simple technique of rearing yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker)

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Insecticide evaluation and host plant resistance studies using YSB have been limited by an inadequate insect supply during certain months. Previous workers made unsatisfactory mass rearing attempts by placing larvae on 40- to 45-d-old rice plants or cut stem pieces of flowering plants, or feeding them artificial diets.

We developed a simple mass rearing technique using healthy booting stage rice plants. IR62 is used as a food plant because it is early maturing, high tillering, and YSB susceptible, but is resistant to several other insects and diseases that may infest a greenhouse culture.